

TWO-PARAMETER CHARACTERIZATION OF CRACK TIP FIELDS IN AN ANISOTROPIC PLATE UNDER BENDING

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SUMMARY: Crack-tip fields in an anisotropic Reissner plate under bending are examined in this paper. An analysis has been conducted recently (Liang and Yuan, 1999) using stress functions to determine the asymptotic crack-tip fields for anisotropic plates. Two-term asymptotic crack tip fields, the leading singular term and non-singular constant stress term or called T-stress, in bending and transverse shear are presented. The path-independent J -integral in bending is used to relate the bending stress intensity factors. In conjunction with finite element analysis, two approaches to determine the T-stresses are reported based on the developed formulation in this paper. Comparison of two-term asymptotic solutions with leading term and finite element solutions in a finite plate under pure bending moment is provided. The coefficients of K_I and M_{II}^c which are deduced from the methods can accurately characterize the crack-tip fields, although these coefficients are obtained from finite element results with larger element size.

1. INTRODUCTION

Crack-tip fields play an significant role in predicting the failure of the solids. In elastic-plastic solids, the HRR solution (Hutchinson, 1968; Rice and Rosengren, 1968) represents the leading singular term of the asymptotic expansion of the crack-tip fields and is uniquely characterized by a parameter J -integral. Using the J -integral as a single characterizing parameter requires J -dominance, that is, the HRR field must dominate over the region where microscopic fracture process occurs. When J -dominance is lost, the single parameter characterization may be insufficient to predict the crack growth initiation. In this case, two-parameter characterization of the crack-tip fields may be necessary.

Asymptotic crack-tip fields with higher order terms in elastic-plastic solids have been of significant interest in the last ten decade (e.g., Li and Wang, 1986 for plane strain mode-I loading; Yuan and Yang, 1995 for anti-plane shear; Yuan and Yang, 1997 for plane stress mode-I loading). An independent parameter associated with higher order terms has been obtained from point matching with displacement or stress components near the crack tip. With the two-parameter characterization, the crack-tip fields can be accurately described in the region of interest. The effect of in-plane geometry (constraint effect) on the crack growth initiation can be explained in some cases.

In linear elastic isotropic solids, the crack-tip fields can be expressed as the eigenfunction expansion (e.g., Williams, 1957). The second-order, nonsingular, term, or called T-stress has been found to be responsible for crack instability and crack turning (e.g. Cotterell and Rice, 1980). The T-stress can be conveniently determined from a J -integral approach with an auxiliary field (Kfourri, 1986). Due to the path-independence of the J -integral, the T-stress can be evaluated away from the crack-tip. Thus a refined mesh to capture the steep stress gradient is unnecessary. Motivated by the crack turning phenomenon observed in the compact-tension specimens of composites (Yuan and Yang, 1998), Yang and Yuan (1999) used the J -integral approach and Betti's reciprocal theorem with auxiliary fields to determine the T-stress terms and the coefficients of the higher-order terms in anisotropic solids.

Recently, The asymptotic crack tip fields in an anisotropic plate under bending, twisting moments, and transverse shear loads have been presented (Yuan and Yang, 1998; Liang and Yuan, 1999) using Stroh formalism and stress function approach respectively. The J -integral for bending was derived and related to the energy release rate using Irwin's formulation. The T-stress terms for bending are evaluated from the displacements along the crack flanks region close to the tip. The objective of the paper is to examine the crack-tip fields using the two-parameter characterization, stress intensity factor and T-stress. In the next section, the governing equations of anisotropic plates based on Reissner plate theory and stress functions are briefly discussed. The asymptotic crack tip solutions, including the singular term and T-stress term, are listed in Section 3. In Section 4, the J -integral and energy release rate for anisotropic Reissner plates are presented and the relationship between J and the stress intensity factors is also obtained. Finally, several examples for a finite plate under pure bending moment are selected for characterizing the crack-tip fields using the stress intensity factors and T-stress with the aid of finite element analysis.

2. BASIC EQUATIONS

In this section the Reissner's equations, which govern the bending of linear anisotropic elastic plates, are presented. Let x_1 - x_2 plane of a three dimensional Cartesian basis coincide with the mid-plane of the plate with thickness h shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Notations of moments, transverse shears and rotations for an anisotropic plate containing a crack with local polar coordinate at a crack tip. The principal material axes, X and Y , are indicated.

A through the thickness crack is located along $-a \leq x_1 \leq a$. Consider a plate that possesses elastic symmetry about the mid-plane $x_3 = 0$, the displacements induced by the bending and transverse shear loads are assumed to be of the form:

$$U_1 = x_3 \psi_1(x_1, x_2), \quad U_2 = x_3 \psi_2(x_1, x_2), \quad U_3 = w(x_1, x_2) \quad (1)$$

where $[U_1, U_2, U_3]^T$ is the actual displacement vector of the plate which is a function of (x_1, x_2, x_3) . ψ_1 and ψ_2 are the rotations of the sections perpendicular to x_1 and x_2 axes respectively. w is the transverse displacements. ψ_1 , ψ_2 , and w are called generalized displacements. The field governing equations for Reissner plate with its top and bottom faces traction-free can be expressed as follow:

The equilibrium equations

$$\begin{aligned} M_{\alpha\beta,\beta} - Q_\alpha &= 0 \\ Q_{\alpha,\alpha} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad \alpha, \beta = 1, 2 \quad (2)$$

where M_{11} , M_{22} , M_{12} are bending and twisting moment resultants appropriate to the rectangular coordinate x_1, x_2, x_3 , and Q_1 and Q_2 denote transverse shear resultants, all per unit length, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned} [M_{11}, M_{22}, M_{12}] &= \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} [\sigma_{11}, \sigma_{22}, \sigma_{12}] x_3 dx_3 \\ [Q_1, Q_2] &= \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} [\sigma_{13}, \sigma_{23}] dx_3 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The following stress distributions along x_3 are assumed

$$\sigma_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{12x_3}{h^3} M_{\alpha\beta}, \quad \alpha, \beta = 1, 2 \quad (4a)$$

$$\sigma_{\alpha 3} = \frac{3}{2h} \left(1 - 4 \frac{x_3^2}{h^2}\right) Q_\alpha, \quad \alpha = 1, 2, \quad \sigma_{33} = 0 \quad (4b)$$

the generalized displacement-stress resultant relations

$$\frac{h}{2} \begin{Bmatrix} \psi_{1,1} \\ \psi_{2,2} \\ \psi_{1,2} + \psi_{2,1} \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{6}{h^2} \begin{bmatrix} s_{11} & s_{12} & s_{16} \\ s_{12} & s_{22} & s_{26} \\ s_{16} & s_{26} & s_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} M_{11} \\ M_{22} \\ M_{12} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad \begin{Bmatrix} w_{,1} + \psi_1 \\ w_{,2} + \psi_2 \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{1}{kh} \begin{bmatrix} s_{55} & s_{45} \\ s_{45} & s_{44} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} Q_1 \\ Q_2 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

in which $k = 5/6$, and s_{ij} are the elastic compliances.

Referring to a polar coordinate system with its origin at the crack tip, the traction-free boundary conditions imposed on the crack surfaces are

$$M_{12} = M_{22} = Q_2 = 0 \quad \text{at } \theta = \pm\pi \quad (6)$$

It is assumed that the plate is also subjected to in-plane loads of sufficient magnitude so there is no crack closure.

Equations (2), (5) along with (6) are the Reissner equations that govern the deformation of anisotropic cracked plates including the transverse shear effect.

Introducing two stress functions, ϕ and χ , such that

$$M_{11} = \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x_2^2} + \chi, \quad M_{22} = \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x_1^2} + \chi, \quad M_{12} = -\frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} \quad (7a)$$

and

$$Q_1 = \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial x_1}, \quad Q_2 = \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial x_2} \quad (7b)$$

It is easily shown that (1a) is automatically satisfied and (1b) requires that $\nabla^2 \chi = 0$. Substitution of (7a) into (5a), the compatibility equation of ψ_i in terms of stress functions ϕ and χ

$$L_4 \phi = R_2 \chi \quad (8)$$

where L_4 and R_2 are differential operators defined by

$$L_4 = s_{11} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_2^4} - 2s_{16} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2^3} + (2s_{12} + s_{66}) \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2^2} - 2s_{26} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^3 \partial x_2} + s_{22} \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^4} \quad (9)$$

$$R_2 = -(s_{11} + s_{12}) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_2^2} + (s_{16} + s_{26}) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} - (s_{12} + s_{22}) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1^2} \quad (10)$$

From (2b) and (5b), one can also have the following equation in terms of generalized displacements

$$L_2 w = -[s_{44}, s_{55}, -s_{45}] \begin{Bmatrix} \psi_{1,1} \\ \psi_{2,2} \\ \psi_{2,1} + \psi_{1,2} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

in which

$$L_2 = s_{55} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_2^2} - 2s_{45} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} + s_{44} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1^2} \quad (12)$$

2. ASYMPTOTIC SOLUTIONS

The asymptotic crack-tip fields up to the second order term are expressed by (Liang and Yuan, 1999)

$$\begin{Bmatrix} M_{11} \\ M_{12} \\ M_{22} \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{h^2}{6} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \operatorname{Re} \left\{ \frac{1}{p_1 - p_2} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{p_2^2}{\sqrt{z_2}} - \frac{p_1^2}{\sqrt{z_1}} & p_1 p_2 \left(\frac{p_2}{\sqrt{z_2}} - \frac{p_1}{\sqrt{z_1}} \right) \\ \frac{p_1}{\sqrt{z_1}} - \frac{p_2}{\sqrt{z_2}} & p_1 p_2 \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{z_1}} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{z_2}} \right) \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{z_2}} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{z_1}} & \frac{p_1}{\sqrt{z_2}} - \frac{p_2}{\sqrt{z_1}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} K_2 \\ K_1 \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} M_{11}^c \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \right\} \quad (13a)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} Q_1 \\ Q_2 \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{2h}{3} \frac{K_3}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \operatorname{Re} \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{p_3}{\sqrt{z_3}} \\ 1 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{z_3}} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} Q_1^c \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \right\} \quad (13b)$$

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \psi_1 \\ \psi_2 \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{h}{2} \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \operatorname{Re} \left\{ \frac{1}{p_1 - p_2} \begin{bmatrix} \xi_2 \sqrt{z_2} - \xi_1 \sqrt{z_1} & p_1 \xi_2 \sqrt{z_2} - p_2 \xi_1 \sqrt{z_1} \\ \eta_2 \sqrt{z_2} - \eta_1 \sqrt{z_1} & p_1 \eta_2 \sqrt{z_2} - p_2 \eta_1 \sqrt{z_1} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} K_2 \\ K_1 \end{Bmatrix} + \frac{h^3}{12} \begin{Bmatrix} M_{11}^c (s_{11} x_1 + s_{16} x_2) \\ M_{11}^c s_{12} x_2 \end{Bmatrix} \right\} \quad (14a)$$

$$w = -\frac{2}{3k\mu} \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} K_3 \operatorname{Im}[\sqrt{z_3}] + \frac{1}{kh} Q_1^c (s_{55}x_1 + s_{45}x_2) \quad (14b)$$

where K_1 , K_2 , and K_3 are the stress intensity factor for bending, twisting, and transverse shear respectively. M_{11}^c and Q_1^c are constant «stress» terms, or called T-stresses.

p_1 and p_2 denote the two roots with positive imaginary parts of the following polynomial equation

$$s_{11}p^4 - 2s_{16}p^3 + (2s_{12} + s_{66})p^2 - 2s_{26}p + s_{22} = 0 \quad (15)$$

p_3 is the root with positive imaginary part of

$$s_{55}p^2 - 2s_{45}p + s_{44} = 0 \quad (16)$$

$$\text{and } \xi_\alpha = s_{11}p_\alpha^2 - s_{16}p_\alpha + s_{12}, \quad \eta_\alpha = s_{12}p_\alpha - s_{26} + s_{22}/p_\alpha, \quad \mu = (s_{44}s_{55} - s_{45}^2)^{-1/2} \quad (17)$$

4. THE J-INTEGRAL AND ENERGY RELEASE RATE

For the plate subjected to bending and transverse shear loads, performing integration of the three-dimensional J -integral through the thickness and using (1), (3), and (4), the J -integral for Reissner plate can be expressed as

$$J = \frac{1}{2} \int_C [M_{\alpha\beta} \kappa_{\alpha\beta} + Q_\alpha \gamma_{\alpha 3}] n_1 ds - \int_C (M_{\alpha\beta} \psi_{\alpha,1} + Q_\beta w_{,1}) n_\beta ds \quad (18)$$

where $\kappa_{\alpha\beta}$, $\gamma_{\alpha 3}$ are the curvatures and transverse shear strains respectively given by

$$\kappa_{11} = \frac{\partial \psi_1}{\partial x_1}, \quad \kappa_{22} = \frac{\partial \psi_2}{\partial x_2}, \quad 2\kappa_{12} = \frac{\partial \psi_1}{\partial x_2} + \frac{\partial \psi_2}{\partial x_1} \quad (19)$$

$$\gamma_{13} = \frac{\partial U_1}{\partial x_3} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x_1} = \psi_1 + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x_1}, \quad \gamma_{23} = \frac{\partial U_2}{\partial x_3} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x_2} = \psi_2 + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x_2} \quad (20)$$

C is a contour in the mid-plane of the plate, \mathbf{n} is the unit outward normal. The zero loading on the top and bottom faces of the plate has been assumed. The path-independent J -integral is particularly useful when related to the stress intensity factors for a crack problem. Here, we present a convenient way to establish the relationship, $J=J(K_1, K_2, K_3)$, from the viewpoint of energy release rate for the cracked plate.

In the absence of body forces and dislocations, J is equal to the energy release rate G when crack is extended along the x_1 -axis. The energy release rate for the cracked plate is expressed by Irwin's formulation (1957),

$$G = \lim_{\Delta a \rightarrow 0} \left\{ \frac{1}{2\Delta a} \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \int_0^{\Delta a} \sigma_{2i}(r, 0, x_3) [U_i(\Delta a - r, \pi, x_3) - U_i(\Delta a - r, -\pi, x_3)] dr dx_3 \right\} \quad (21)$$

where Δa is the increment of the crack length. With (1) and (4), G can be written as

$$G = \lim_{\Delta a \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{1}{2\Delta a} \int_0^{\Delta a} \{ [M_{12}, M_{22}] \Big|_{x_1=r}^{x_2=0} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Delta \psi_1 \\ \Delta \psi_2 \end{array} \right\} + Q_2 \Big|_{x_1=r}^{x_2=0} \Delta w \} dr \right] \quad (22)$$

where $\Delta\psi_1 = \psi_1(\Delta a - r, \pi) - \psi_1(\Delta a - r, -\pi)$ and $\Delta w = w(\Delta a - r, \pi) - w(\Delta a - r, -\pi)$.

As $\Delta a \rightarrow 0$, using the leading-order terms in (13), (14), (22) leads to

$$G = \frac{h}{6} s_{11} \text{Im}[(p_1 + p_2)K_2^2 + 2p_1p_2K_2K_1 + (\bar{p}_1 + \bar{p}_2)p_1p_2K_1^2] + \frac{2h}{9k} \frac{K_3^2}{\mu} \quad (23)$$

5. NUMERICAL RESULTS AND SUMMARY

The asymptotic solutions for the anisotropic plate is valid for any type of loading conditions and finite geometry, yet the coefficients associated with the singular and higher-order terms cannot be determined by asymptotic analysis alone. These coefficients, in general, need to be determined from numerical methods. The objective of this section is to examine the crack-tip fields using the two-parameter characterization, stress intensity factor and T-stress. The bending stress intensity factor can be calculated through the J -integral, (18) together with (23) for a single fracture mode, or through a virtual crack closure technique (Rybicki and Kanninen, 1977). T-stress terms can be determined from the asymptotic displacements along the crack flanks.

In the virtual crack closure technique, the energy release rate is computed by multiplying the nodal moments and transverse shear forces, $M_{22}^a, M_{22}^b, M_{12}^a, M_{12}^b, Q_2^a$ and Q_2^b at crack tip node a and its adjacent node b and the corresponding relative nodal generalized displacements, $(\psi_2^c - \psi_2^{c'}), (\psi_2^d - \psi_2^{d'}), (\psi_1^c - \psi_1^{c'}), (\psi_1^d - \psi_1^{d'}), (w^c - w^{c'})$ and $(w^d - w^{d'})$, at nodes c and d as indicated in Fig. 2. The eight-node isoparametric plate elements are utilized near the crack tip and the nodal forces at a are the summation of nodal forces from element m and n at node a . The formula used to calculate energy release rate by this technique can be written as

Fig. 2: Plate finite-element mesh scheme near the crack tip

$$G = \frac{1}{2\Delta a} \left[\begin{aligned} &M_{22}^a(\psi_2^c - \psi_2^{c'}) + M_{22}^b(\psi_2^d - \psi_2^{d'}) \\ &+ M_{12}^a(\psi_1^c - \psi_1^{c'}) + M_{12}^b(\psi_1^d - \psi_1^{d'}) \\ &+ Q_2^a(w^c - w^{c'}) + Q_2^b(w^d - w^{d'}) \end{aligned} \right] \quad (24)$$

where Δa is the length of the element ahead and behind of the crack tip. The physical interpretation of (24) is the amount of work required to close the crack in a length Δa . This method based on the work concept allows us to use relatively coarse meshes near the tip in the finite element analysis.

The asymptotic solution of asymptotic displacement (15) on the crack flank surfaces, $\theta = \pm\pi$, can be used to evaluate T-stress. Considering the displacements of two points, (r, π) and $(r, -\pi)$ which are close to the crack tip and located on the upper and lower crack flanks respectively and integrating the generalized displacement-stress resultant relations directly leads to the expressions for M_{11}^c and Q_1^c

$$M_{11}^c = -\frac{h^3}{24s_{11}r}[\psi_1(r, \pi) + \psi_1(r, -\pi) - 2\psi_1^0] + O(r) \quad (25)$$

$$Q_1^c = -\frac{hk}{2s_{55}r}[w(r, \pi) + w(r, -\pi) - 2w^0] + O(r) \quad (26)$$

For the displacement approach for T-stress evaluation, it should be noticed that the rigid body rotation and transverse displacements, ψ_1^0 and w^0 , contained in (25) and (26) must be extracted out to determine T-stress.

In addition, the T-stresses can also be determined by a «strain» approach. Rewriting (25) and (26) in the form

$$\Sigma\psi_1 = 2\left(-\frac{12}{h^3}s_{11}M_{11}^c r + \psi_1^0\right) + O(r^2) \quad (27)$$

$$\Sigma w = 2\left(-\frac{s_{55}}{kh}Q_1^c r + w^0\right) + O(r^2) \quad (28)$$

where $\Sigma\psi_1 = \psi_1(r, \pi) + \psi_1(r, -\pi)$ and $\Sigma w = w(r, \pi) + w(r, -\pi)$.

Taking the derivative of (27) and (28) with respect to r gives

$$\begin{aligned} M_{11}^c &= -\frac{h^3}{24s_{11}} \frac{d\Sigma\psi_1}{dr} = \frac{h^3}{24s_{11}} \Sigma\psi_{1,1} = \frac{h^3}{24s_{11}} \Sigma\kappa_{11} \\ Q_1^c &= -\frac{kh}{2s_{55}} \frac{d\Sigma w}{dr} = \frac{kh}{2s_{55}} \Sigma w_{,1} = \frac{kh}{2s_{55}} \Sigma\gamma_{13} \end{aligned} \quad \text{as } r \rightarrow 0 \quad (29)$$

It can be seen that the T-stresses, M_{11}^c and Q_1^c , can be calculated by the sum of the curvature κ_{11} and transverse shear strain γ_{13} at the top and bottom crack flank regions close to the tip, respectively. T-stress can be accurately evaluated from the flanks as long as the strain or displacement on the crack flanks near the crack tip is effectively determined. Note that if regular finite elements are used for modeling, the T-stress, in general, is calculated from the locations starting from the third element behind the crack tip due to numerical errors close to the singular region.

The following calculations focus on an AS4 carbon warp-knit fabric composite plate. The materials properties (Liang and Yuan, 1999) are:

$$\begin{aligned} E_X &= 5.09 \text{ Msi}, & E_Y &= 11.21 \text{ Msi}, & E_Z &= 1.53 \text{ Msi} \\ G_{XY} &= 2.77 \text{ Msi}, & G_{YZ} &= 0.64 \text{ Msi}, & G_{XZ} &= 0.57 \text{ Msi} \\ \nu_{XY} &= 0.20, & \nu_{XZ} &= 0.29, & \nu_{YZ} &= 0.22 \end{aligned}$$

where X and Y represent the 90^0 and 0^0 fiber directions respectively, Z is the through the thickness direction.

The composite plate shown in Fig. 3 has a geometry, $L = 20$ in., $2W = 10$ in.. The crack size $a/W = 0.5$ and thickness $h = 1$ in. are used in this numerical study. The plate is under a uniform moment $M_{22} = M_o = 1,000$ lb. (moment per unit length). In the first set of numerical results (not shown here) where the crack orientations are either parallel or perpendicular to the 0° fiber direction of the composite, the crack behavior is pure mode-I. Thus K_1 can be directly determined from the J-integral where the integral can be evaluated away from the tip. Numerical results showed that there is an excellent agreement of K_1 values obtained from the J-integral and energy release rate G calculated from the virtual crack closure technique, although the crack-tip fields, especially for stress or strain, are not accurate for the first element ahead and behind the crack tip. Figs. 4 - 6 display the comparisons of two-term asymptotic solutions of M_{11}/M_o with the leading term and finite element solutions. In these figures, the comparison is made along the $\theta = 0$ and 90 degrees for isotropic solids and AS4 fabric composites with two material orientations, namely the crack perpendicular and parallel to the 0° fibers. In the isotropic case, $E = 11.21$ Msi and $\nu = 0.3$ are used. The K_1 and M_{11}^c values are first evaluated and listed as follows:

- (a) Isotropic solids: $K_1 = 13.66 \text{ ksi} \sqrt{\text{in}}$ and $M_{11}^c = -1.034 \text{ ksi}$
- (b) AS4 fabric composites (crack parallel to 0° fibers): $K_1 = 15.22 \text{ ksi} \sqrt{\text{in}}$ and $M_{11}^c = -1.549 \text{ ksi}$
- (c) AS4 fabric composites (crack perpendicular to 0° fibers): $K_1 = 14.69 \text{ ksi} \sqrt{\text{in}}$ and $M_{11}^c = -0.715 \text{ ksi}$

The leading term and two-term solutions for M_{11} can then be obtained from (13a). From these figures, it is obviously seen that the two-term characterization of the crack-tip fields agrees well with crack-tip fields obtained from finite element analysis, and improves the leading singular term solution. Since M_{11}^c is compressive, the K-field overestimates the stress prediction at a finite distance from the tip. For any other angles, the same conclusion can be made.

Fig. 3: A center-cracked composite plate under bending moment M_o

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Fig. 4: Comparison of two-term asymptotic solution with leading term and finite element solutions at $\theta = 0^\circ$ and 90° of isotropic solids

Fig. 5: Comparison of two-term asymptotic solution with leading term and finite element solutions at $\theta = 0^\circ$ and 90° of the composite with 0° fibers parallel to the crack

Fig. 6: Comparison of two-term asymptotic solution with leading term and finite element solutions at $\theta = 0^\circ$ and 90° of the composite with 0° fibers perpendicular to the crack